

YOGA PRACTICE HELPS IN SPORT AND GAMES

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Abstract:

Yoga is a profound system of holistic health which originated in India over 5,000 years ago. It was first put into written form as the Yoga Sutras by Patanjali.

- ✓ Karma Yoga: the way of right action
- ✓ Bhakti Yoga: the way of devotion
- ✓ Jnana Yoga: the way of knowledge
- ✓ Raja Yoga: The path of willpower

Physical Benefits:

Yoga creates a toned, flexible, and strong body in order to improve respiration, energy, and vitality. It helps to maintain a balanced metabolism, promotes cardio and circulatory health and relieves pain. It also helps you look and feel younger than your age while improving your athletic performance.

Mental Benefits:

Yoga helps you relax and handle stressful and anxiety situations more easily. It teaches you how to quiet the mind so you can focus your energy where you want it to go — into a difficult yoga pose, on the tennis court or golf course. Yoga encourages positive thoughts and self-acceptance.

Benefits of Yoga in Sport –Teamwork /Cooperation Participation

Confidence / Self-Esteem Positive Outlet / Forum for Expression / Psychosocial Awareness and Respect for Body, Self, Others

Skills, Communication, Social Interaction, Interpersonal Tolerance / Conflict Resolution Skills Integrates Communities, Families.

In Yoga, the body is treated with care and respect for it is the primary instrument in man's work and growth. Yoga Exercises improve circulation, stimulate the abdominal organs, and put pressure on the glandular system of the body, which can generally result to better health.

Breathing techniques were developed based on the concept that breath is the source of life. In Yoga, students gain breathing control as they slowly increase their breathing.

In Meditation, sportsman brings the activities of the mind into focus resulting in a 'quiet' mind. By designing physical poses and Breathing Techniques that develop awareness of our body.

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